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Research article

Ritonavir and Covid-19 infection - additional hope of light at the end of a dark tunnel?

Ilija Barukčić¹

¹ Internist, Horandstrasse, 26441 Jever, Germany

* **Correspondence:** E-Mail: Barukcic@t-online.de; Tel: +49-4466-333; Fax: +49-4466-333.

Abstract:

Background:

There are many ways to reach a goal, but only those who swim against the tide fights their way to the source. Those who floats with the current, floats critical steps back, ahead of the competition. Is Pfizer Inc. quite consciously swimming against the current?

Methods:

The data presented by Pfizer Inc. on the relationship between ritonavir and Covid-19 infection were re-analysed by new statistical methods.

Results:

Under conditions that the data as announced publicly by Pfizer Inc. can be reproduced by other, the drug ritonavir excludes a death due to a Covid-19 infection.

Conclusion:

The light at the end of a tunnel is becoming brighter. Ritonavir is of help against a Covid-19 infection.

Keywords: Study design; Bias; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k

1. Introduction

The first documented, large-scale outbreak of the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) infection in central China in December 2019 resulted globally in a very serious pandemic. At present, it is very difficult to get this pandemic quickly under control. Among the various anti-COVID-19 measures are different vaccines like heterologous ¹, ², ³ recombinant (adeno-) virus

¹Sputnik V, Russia NCT04530396 PMID: 33545094

²AstraZeneca, Sweden/Great Britain PMID: 33617777

³Johnson and Johnson PMID: 33882225

(rAd)-based vaccines, RNA vaccines^{4, 5}, DNA vaccines⁶ and other vaccines⁷ too. Anti-SARS-CoV-2 monoclonal antibodies like ronapreve⁸ and the recombinant human monoclonal antibody regdanvimab (RegkironaTM)⁹ are of use too. Anti-SARS-CoV-2 monoclonal antibodies neutralizes SARS-CoV-2¹⁰ by binding to the receptor binding domain of the SARS-CoV-2 virus spike protein. An effective oral anti SARS-CoV-2 virus treatment (molnupiravir¹¹, ritonavir) is another strategy to get the current Covid-19 pandemics under control. On Friday, November 05, 2021 - 06:45am, PfizerTM Inc. announced¹² publicly that no deaths in patients who received ritonavir¹³ (PAXLOVIDTM) were found in the Phase 2/3 EPIC-HR (Evaluation of Protease Inhibition for COVID-19 in High-Risk Patients) randomized, double-blind study¹⁴ of non-hospitalized adult patients with COVID-19 viral infection compared to 10 deaths in patients who received placebo. PAXLOVIDTM (PF-07321332; ritonavir) was found to reduce the risk of death by 89%¹⁵. The data of the ritonavir study were re-analysed.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Data

2.2. Study design

A study design should be fair and representative as much as possible in order to assure data, which we can rely on and work with. The index of unfairness (Barukčić, 2019a) and the index of independence (Barukčić, 2019b) are indicating to which extent data could be biased due to study design. Under ideal conditions, it is desirable that $p(\text{IOU}) = 0$ or $p(\text{IOI}) = 0$ or that even $p(\text{IOU}) = p(\text{IOI}) = 0$.

Table 1. The quality of data (see Barukčić, 2019a, p. 25)

p(IOI)	Quality of study design
$0 < p(\text{IOI}) \leq 0,25$	Unfair study design
$0,25 < p(\text{IOI}) \leq 0,5$	Very unfair study design
$0,5 < p(\text{IOI}) \leq 0,75$	Highly unfair study design
$0,75 < p(\text{IOI}) \leq 1,0$	Extremely unfair study design

2.2.1. Quality of data

Decisions should be based on high quality of data. However, we are continually asking ourselves can we and to which extent are we allowed to rely on the data published. Data integrity issues in Pfizer's

⁴ComirnatyTM (BiontechTM / PfizerTM), Germany PMID: 33301246

⁵ModernaTM, USA PMID: 33378609

⁶DNA SARS-CoV-2 vaccine (ZyCoV-D), India PMID: 34308319

⁷Cell Death Differ PMID: 33479399

⁸RegeneronTM, Suisse PMID: 34743612

⁹RegkironaTM or Regdanvimab, South Korea PMID: 34724174

¹⁰Cheolmin Kim et al., South Korea

¹¹Molnupiravir, MSDTM

¹²PfizerTM Inc., Friday, November 05, 2021 - 06:45am

¹³NCT number: NCT04960202

¹⁴COVID-19 clinicaltrials

¹⁵PAXLOVIDTM, PfizerTM Inc.

vaccine trial ¹⁶ have become public. Poor practices at clinical trials of different kind ¹⁷ raise questions about the quality of data published and can be suitable to diminish the public trust in a safe and effective Covid-19 vaccine. It is unavoidable that the data provided to the public have to be treated with some caution. However, it has to be ascertained that the quality of the data will be further improved. Besides of these improvements, data should be made freely publicly available in detail while following a certain standard. There are accurate mathematical methods to check data for integrity, while few of them are already discussed ¹⁸ in the literature.

2.2.2. Phase 2/3 EPIC-HR (Evaluation of Protease Inhibition for COVID-19 in High-Risk Patients)

None of patients treated with ritonavir within five days of symptom onset died (0/607). However, 10 of 612 patients who received a placebo died (10/612). The data announced publicly are presented by table 2 and analysed.

¹⁶Paul D Thacker, investigative journalist PMID: 34728500

¹⁷The British Medical Journal PMID: 34728500

¹⁸Hong Chen et al. PMID: 25087521

Table 2. Ritonavir and (Covid-19) death (EPIC-HR study).

		(Covid-19) death		
		YES	NO	
Ritonavir	YES	0	607	607
	NO	10	602	612
		10	1209	1219

Statistical analysis.Causal relationship $k = -0,0905744038$

p Value left tailed (HGD) = 0,0009805

p (SINE) = 0,9917965546 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — B_t) = 10,0000 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — A_t) = 0,1634

p Value (SINE) = 0,0081698890

p (IMP) = 0,5020508614 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP — A_t) = 607,0000 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP — B_t) = 304,7552

p Value (IMP) = 0,3922241536

p (SINE \cap IMP) = 0,4938474159 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE \cap IMP)₁ = 607,1634 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE \cap IMP)₂ = 314,7552p Value (SINE \cap IMP) = 0,3972**p (EXCL) = 1,0000000000** $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL — A_t) = 0,0000 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL — B_t) = 0,0000

p Value (EXCL) = 0,0000000000

Relative risk (RR).

RR (nc) = 0,0000

RR (sc) = 0,0000

Additional measures.

OR = 0,4938

IOR = -1,0000

Study design.

p(IOU) = 0,493847416

p(IOI) = 0,489745693

 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (p(IOU) = p(IOI)) = 589,6641

The hyper-geometric distribution describes the probability of x successes in N **draws without replacement** while the same distribution is valid for all sample sizes. In contrast to the hyper-geometric distribution, the binomial distribution which describes the probability of x successes in N **draws with replacement**. The left tailed p Value is used when the alternative to independence is that there is a **negative relationship** between the variables investigated. The left tailed p Value (no replacement,

hyper-geometric distribution) is calculated as follows:

$$pValue_{\text{left tailed}}(X \leq 0) \equiv \sum_{t=0}^0 \left(\frac{\binom{607}{t} \times \binom{1219-607}{10-t}}{\binom{1219}{10}} \right) \quad (2.1)$$

$$\equiv 0,0009805082$$

In other words, both events, Ritonavir and (Covid-19) death , might occur together at the same (period of) time t purely by chance at a probability rate of 0,0009805082 . The data published indicate a highly significant statistical result.

2.2.3. EPIC-HR (condition: fair (b=c) study design)

Table 3. Ritonavir and (Covid-19) death (fair study design).

		(Covid-19) death		
		YES	NO	
Ritonavir	YES	0	607	607
	NO	607	39860	40467
		607	40467	41074

Statistical analysis.Causal relationship $k = -0,0149998764$

p Value left tailed (HGD) = 0,0001111

p (SINE) = 0,9852217948 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — B_t) = 607,0000 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — A_t) = 9,1049

p Value (SINE) = 0,0146695435

p (IMP) = 0,9852217948 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP — A_t) = 607,0000 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP — B_t) = 9,1049

p Value (IMP) = 0,0146695435

p (SINE \cap IMP) = 0,9704435896 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE \cap IMP)₁ = 616,1049 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE \cap IMP)₂ = 616,1049p Value (SINE \cap IMP) = 0,0291**p (EXCL) = 1,0000000000** $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL — A_t) = 0,0000 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL — B_t) = 0,0000

p Value (EXCL) = 0,0000000000

Relative risk (RR).

RR (nc) = 0,0000

RR (sc) = 0,0000

Additional measures.

OR = 0,9704

IOR = -1,0000

Study design.

p(IOU) = 0,97044359

p(IOI) = 0

 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (p(IOU) = p(IOI)) = 19.340,9407

It is appropriate to lose view thoughts about a fair study design. Let us assume that a drug (ritonavir) helps against an illness (Covid-19). Due to several aspects, it is decided that n=607 patient should be treated with ritonavir (verum). The question arises of how to calculate the size of the placebo group?

Under normal circumstances, the death rate of a population which is age dependent varies around 1-1.5 %. The study design has to ensure fair experimental conditions in order to enable the investigator to prove a hypothesis. Under this condition, it is necessary that $b = c = 607$ or that $c = 607$. In other words, the value of c is known as $c = 607$ (see table 3). In general, it is $((c/X)*100) = 1-1.5 \%$ while X might denote the size of the placebo population. In our case, it is $((607/X)*100) = 1.5 \%$. The size of the placebo population, denoted by X , follows as $X = ((607/1.5)*100) = 40466,6$ individuals or 40467. In general, it is $X = ((c/\text{death rate in per cent})*100)$.

The fictive data (see table 3) indicate a significant *conditio sine qua non* relationship (p Value = 0.0146695435, $N = 41074$), a significant *conditio per quam* relationship (p Value = 0.0146695435, $N = 41074$) and a significant necessary and sufficient condition relationship (p Value = 0.0291, $N = 41074$). In other words, we have to conclude that ritonavir is the cause of the death of patients. However, this is deemed to be incompatible with the following fact. It is also true that the exclusion relationship is highly significant (p Value (EXCL) = 0.0, $N = 41074$) or ritonavir is not the cause of the death of patients. Thus far, what is true? First, the data used are of very good quality ($p(\text{IOI}) = 0$) and can be used to test for causal relationship k . The causal relationship k is negative and highly significant, which excludes the possibility that a necessary condition or a sufficient condition and necessary and sufficient condition can be accepted. This rather trivial fact is explicitly stressed once again by and $\text{IOR} = -1.0$ and $p(\text{IOU}) = 0.97044359$. A $p(\text{IOU})$ of 0.97044359 indicates that the data analysed are extremely biased and cannot be used to test the same for a necessary and a sufficient condition. Second. In order to prove all relationships by the same study, the study design should ensure that $p(\text{IOU}) = p(\text{IOI}) = 0$, which is not the case as indicated by a $\tilde{\chi}^2 (p(\text{IOU}) = p(\text{IOI})) = 19.340,9407$. The original study design ensured that $p(\text{IOU}) = p(\text{IOI})$ with a $\tilde{\chi}^2 (p(\text{IOU}) = p(\text{IOI})) = 589,6641$ but not that $p(\text{IOU}) = p(\text{IOI}) = 0$.

2.3. Methods

The nature of definitions is discussed by scientist since ancient times. Many times, several different kinds of definitions are necessary to solve a scientific issue properly. Even if often in play, inappropriate definitions can lead to logical fallacies too.

2.3.1. The number +0

Definition 2.1 (The number +0). *Let i denote the imaginary number (Bombelli, 1579). The imaginary number i is known to be defined solely by the property that its square is -1 . According to today valid rules of algebra, the number +0 is defined as the expression*

$$+0 \equiv +1 \times +0 \equiv +0 \times +1 \equiv +1 - 1 \equiv +1 + i^2 \equiv +1 + e^{i\pi} \equiv \neg(+1) \quad (2.2)$$

while '=' or \equiv denotes the equals sign (Recorde, 1557) or equality sign (Rolle, 1690) used to indicate equality and '-' (Widmann, 1489; Pacioli, 1494) denotes minus signs used to represent the operations of subtraction and the notions of negative as well and '+' denotes the plus (Recorde, 1557) signs used to represent the operations of addition and the notions of positive as well. Negation is denoted by \neg .

Remark 2.1. Roger Cotes (1682 – 1716) (Cotes and Halley, 1714) or Leonhard Euler's (1707 – 1783) identity (Euler, 1748) is regarded as one of the most beautiful equations (Wilson, 2018). In this context, it is provisionally presumed, that Euler's identity (Euler, 1748) is logically sound and correct.

2.3.2. The number +1

Definition 2.2 (The number +1). According to today valid rules of algebra, the number +1 is defined as the expression

$$+1 \equiv +1 + 0 \equiv +1 - 0 \equiv -(+0) \quad (2.3)$$

while again '=' or \equiv may denote the equals sign (Recorde, 1557) or equality sign (Rolle, 1690) used to indicate equality and '-' (Widmann, 1489; Pacioli, 1494) denotes minus signs used to represent the operations of subtraction and the notions of negative as well and '+' denotes the plus (Recorde, 1557) signs used to represent the operations of addition and the notions of positive as well.

2.3.3. Single event distribution

Let a **random variable** (Gosset, 1914) X denote something like a function defined on a probability space, which itself maps from the sample space (Neyman and Pearson, 1933) to the real numbers. A single event distribution is more or less a discrete probability distribution of any random variable X which takes a certain (observer independent) single value X_t at a **Bernoulli trial** (Uspensky, 1937, p. 45) (period of time) t with the probability $p(X_t)$. The same random variable X takes a certain single anti value \underline{X}_t at a Bernoulli trial (period of time) t with the probability $1-p(X_t)$. There are conditions in nature where a random variable X can take only the values either +0 or +1. Under these conditions the random variable X takes the value 1 with probability $p(X_t = +1)$ and the value 0 with probability $q(X_t = +0) = 1 - p(X_t = +1)$ while the single event distribution passes over into the **Bernoulli distribution**, named after Swiss mathematician Jacob Bernoulli (Bernoulli, 1713). Less formally, many times, the Bernoulli distribution is represented by a (possibly not biased) coin toss where 1 and 0 would represent 'heads' and 'tails' (or vice versa), respectively. However, the relationship between random variables (Gosset, 1914) can be investigated by many (Gosset, 1908) methods, including the tools of probability theory, too.

Definition 2.3 (Two by two table of single event random variables).

The two by two or contingency table which has been introduced by Karl Pearson (Pearson, 1904) in 1904 harbours still a large variety of topics and debates. Central to this is the problem to apply the laws of classical logic on data sets, which concerns the justification of inferences which extrapolate from sample data to general facts. Nevertheless, a contingency table is still an appropriate theoretical model too for studying the relationships between random variables, including *Bernoulli* (Bernoulli, 1713) (*i.e.* +0/+1) distributed random variables existing or occurring at the same *Bernoulli trial* (Uspensky, 1937) (period of time) t .

In this context, let a random variable A at the *Bernoulli trial* (Uspensky, 1937) (period of time) t , denoted by A_t , indicate a risk factor, a condition, a cause et cetera and occur or exist with the probability $p(A_t)$ at the *Bernoulli trial* (Uspensky, 1937) (period of time) t . Let $E(A_t)$ denote the expectation value of A_t . In general it is

$$p(A_t) \equiv p(a_t) + p(b_t) \quad (2.4)$$

The expectation value $E(A_t)$ follows as

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(A_t) &\equiv A_t \times p(A_t) \\
 &\equiv A_t \times (p(a_t) + p(b_t)) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times p(a_t)) + (A_t \times p(b_t)) \\
 &\equiv E(a_t) + E(b_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.5}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(A_t) &\equiv A_t \times p(A_t) \\
 &\equiv (+0 + 1) \times p(A_t) \\
 &\equiv p(A_t) \\
 &\equiv p(a_t) + p(b_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.6}$$

Furthermore, it is

$$p(\underline{A}_t) \equiv p(c_t) + p(d_t) \equiv (1 - p(A_t)) \tag{2.7}$$

The expectation value $E(\underline{A}_t)$ is given as

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(\underline{A}_t) &\equiv A_t \times (1 - p(A_t)) \\
 &\equiv A_t \times (p(c_t) + p(d_t)) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times p(c_t)) + (A_t \times p(d_t)) \\
 &\equiv E(c_t) + E(d_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.8}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(\underline{A}_t) &\equiv A_t \times (1 - p(A_t)) \\
 &\equiv (+0 + 1) \times (1 - p(A_t)) \\
 &\equiv (1 - p(A_t)) \\
 &\equiv p(c_t) + p(d_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.9}$$

Let a random variable B at the *Bernoulli trial* (Uspensky, 1937) (period of time) t , denoted by B_t , indicate an outcome, a conditioned, an effect et cetera and occur or exist with the probability $p(B_t)$ at the *Bernoulli trial* (Uspensky, 1937) (period of time) t . Let $E(B_t)$ denote the expectation value of B_t . In general it is

$$p(B_t) \equiv p(a_t) + p(c_t) \tag{2.10}$$

The expectation value $E(B_t)$ is given by the equation

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(B_t) &\equiv B_t \times p(B_t) \\
 &\equiv B_t \times (p(a_t) + p(c_t)) \\
 &\equiv (B_t \times p(a_t)) + (B_t \times p(c_t)) \\
 &\equiv E(a_t) + E(c_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.11}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(B_t) &\equiv B_t \times p(B_t) \\
 &\equiv (+0 + 1) \times p(B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(a_t) + p(c_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.12}$$

Furthermore, it is

$$p(\underline{B}_t) \equiv p(b_t) + p(d_t) \equiv (1 - p(B_t)) \tag{2.13}$$

The expectation value $E(\underline{B}_t)$ is given by the equation

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(\underline{B}_t) &\equiv B_t \times (1 - p(B_t)) \\
 &\equiv B_t \times (p(b_t) + p(d_t)) \\
 &\equiv (B_t \times p(b_t)) + (B_t \times p(d_t)) \\
 &\equiv E(b_t) + E(d_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.14}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(\underline{B}_t) &\equiv B_t \times (1 - p(B_t)) \\
 &\equiv (+0 + 1) \times (1 - p(B_t)) \\
 &\equiv (1 - p(B_t)) \\
 &\equiv p(b_t) + p(d_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.15}$$

Let $p(a_t) = p(A_t \wedge B_t)$ denote the joint probability distribution of A_t and B_t at the same Bernoulli trial (period of time) t . In general, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(a_t) &\equiv E(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times B_t) \times p(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times B_t) \times p(a_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.16}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(a_t) &\equiv E(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times B_t) \times p(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv ((+0 + 1) \times (+0 + 1)) \times p(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(a_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.17}$$

Let $p(b_t) = p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t)$ denote the joint probability distribution of A_t and not B_t at the same Bernoulli trial (period of time) t . In general, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(b_t) &\equiv E(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(b_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.18}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(b_t) &\equiv E(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv ((+0 + 1) \times (+0 + 1)) \times p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(b_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.19}$$

Let $p(c_t) = p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t)$ denote the joint probability distribution of not A_t and B_t at the same Bernoulli trial (period of time) t . In general, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(c_t) &\equiv E(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \times p(c_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.20}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(c_t) &\equiv E(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \times B_t) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv ((+0 + 1) \times (+0 + 1)) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(c_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.21}$$

Let $p(d_t) = p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t)$ denote the joint probability distribution of not A_t and not B_t at the same Bernoulli trial (period of time) t . In general, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(d_t) &\equiv E(\neg A_t \times \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(d_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.22}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(d_t) &\equiv E(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv ((+0 + 1) \times (+0 + 1)) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(d_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.23}$$

In general, it is

$$p(a_t) + p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) \equiv +1 \tag{2.24}$$

Table 4 provide us with an overview of the definitions above.

Table 4. The two by two table of Bernoulli random variables

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(A_t)$
	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

2.3.4. Binomial random variables

Definition 2.4 (Two by two table of Binomial random variables).

Let $a, b, c, d, A, \underline{A}, B,$ and \underline{B} denote expectation values. Under conditions where *the probability of an event, an outcome, a success et cetera is constant from Bernoulli trial to Bernoulli trial t* , it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 A &= N \times E(A_t) \\
 &\equiv N \times (A_t \times p(A_t)) \\
 &\equiv N \times (p(A_t) + p(B_t)) \\
 &\equiv N \times p(A_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.25}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 B &= N \times E(B_t) \\
 &\equiv N \times (B_t \times p(B_t)) \\
 &\equiv N \times (p(A_t) + p(c_t)) \\
 &\equiv N \times p(B_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.26}$$

where N might denote the population or even the sample size. Furthermore, it is

$$a \equiv N \times (E(A_t)) \equiv N \times (p(A_t)) \tag{2.27}$$

and

$$b \equiv N \times (E(B_t)) \equiv N \times (p(B_t)) \tag{2.28}$$

and

$$c \equiv N \times (E(c_t)) \equiv N \times (p(c_t)) \tag{2.29}$$

and

$$d \equiv N \times (E(d_t)) \equiv N \times (p(d_t)) \tag{2.30}$$

and

$$a + b + c + d \equiv A + \underline{A} \equiv B + \underline{B} \equiv N \tag{2.31}$$

Table 5 provide us again an overview of a two by two table of Binomial random variables.

Table 5. The two by two table of Binomial random variables

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition A_t	TRUE	a	b	A
	FALSE	c	d	\underline{A}
		B	\underline{B}	N

2.3.5. Independence

Definition 2.5 (Independence).

In general, an event A_t at the Bernoulli trial t need not but can be independent of the existence or of the occurrence of another event B_t at the same Bernoulli trial t . Mathematically, independence (Moivre, 1718; Kolmogoroff, 1933) in terms of probability theory is defined at the same (period of) time t (i.e. Bernoulli trial t) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \wedge B_t) &\equiv p(A_t) \times p(B_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (A_t \wedge B_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{N \times (p(a_t))}{N} \equiv 1 - p(A_t | B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \uparrow B_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.32}$$

2.3.6. Dependence

Definition 2.6 (Dependence).

The dependence of events (Barukčić, 1989, p. 57-61) is defined as

$$p\left(\underbrace{A_t \wedge B_t \wedge C_t \wedge \dots}_n\right) \equiv \sqrt[n]{\underbrace{p(A_t) \times p(B_t) \times p(C_t) \times \dots}_n} \tag{2.33}$$

2.3.7. Exclusion relationship

Definition 2.7 (Exclusion relationship [EXCL]).

Mathematically, the exclusion (EXCL) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t | B_t)$ in terms of statistics and

probability theory, is defined (Barukčić, 1989, p. 68-70) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t | B_t) &\equiv p(A_t \uparrow B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (A_t \vee B_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{b + c + d}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{b + A}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{c + B}{N} \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.34}$$

Based on the 1913 Henry Maurice Sheffer (1882-1964) relationship, the Sheffer stroke (Sheffer, 1913; Nicod, 1917) usually denoted by \uparrow , it is $p(A_t \wedge B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t | B_t)$ (see table 6).

Table 6. A_t excludes B_t and vice versa.

		Conditioned (COVID-19) B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition (Vaccine)	TRUE	+0	$p(b_t)$	$p(A_t)$
	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

Remark 2.2. Pfizer Inc. and BioNTech SE announced on Monday, November 09, 2020 - 06:45am results from a Phase 3 COVID-19 vaccine trial with 43,538 participants which provides evidence that their vaccine (BNT162b2) is preventing COVID-19 in participants without evidence of prior SARS-CoV-2 infection. In toto, 170 confirmed cases of COVID-19 were evaluated, with 8 in the vaccine group versus 162 in the placebo group. The exclusion relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(\text{Vaccine : BNT162b2} | \text{COVID - 19(infection)}) &\equiv p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) \\
 &\equiv 1 - p(a_t) \\
 &\equiv 1 - \left(\frac{8}{43538} \right) \\
 &\equiv +0,99981625
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.35}$$

with a P Value = 0,000184.

2.3.8. The goodness of fit test of an exclusion relationship

Definition 2.8 (The χ^2 goodness of fit test of an exclusion relationship).

Under some well known circumstances, testing hypothesis about an exclusion relationship $p(A_t | B_t)$ is possible by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution) too. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of an exclusion relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t | B_t) | A) &\equiv \frac{(b - (a + b))^2}{A} + \frac{((c + d) - \underline{A})^2}{\underline{A}} \\ &\equiv \frac{a^2}{A} + 0 \\ &\equiv \frac{a^2}{A}\end{aligned}\tag{2.36}$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t | B_t) | B) &\equiv \frac{(c - (a + c))^2}{B} + \frac{((b + d) - \underline{B})^2}{\underline{B}} \\ &\equiv \frac{a^2}{B} + 0 \\ &\equiv \frac{a^2}{B}\end{aligned}\tag{2.37}$$

and can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level of significance α . The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution equals zero when the observed values are equal to the expected/theoretical values of an exclusion relationship/distribution $p(A_t | B_t)$, in which case the null hypothesis has to be accepted. Yate's (Yates, 1934) continuity correction was not used under these circumstances.

2.3.9. The left-tailed p Value of an exclusion relationship

Definition 2.9 (The left-tailed p Value of an exclusion relationship).

It is known that as a sample size, N , increases, a sampling distribution of a special test statistic approaches the normal distribution (central limit theorem). Under these circumstances, the left-tailed (lt) p Value (Barukčić, 2019c) of an exclusion relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}pValue_{lt}(A_t | B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t|B_t))} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-(a/N)}\end{aligned}\tag{2.38}$$

A low p-value may provide some evidence of statistical significance.

2.3.10. Neither nor conditions

Definition 2.10 (Neither A_t nor B_t conditions [NOR]).

Mathematically, a neither A_t nor B_t condition (or rejection according to the French philosopher and logician Jean George Pierre Nicod (1893-1924), i.e. Jean Nicod's statement (Nicod, 1924)) relationship (NOR), denoted by $p(A_t \downarrow B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (Barukčić, 1989, p. 68-70) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \downarrow B_t) &\equiv p(d_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{N - \sum_{t=1}^N (A_t \vee B_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (\underline{A}_t \wedge \underline{B}_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{N \times (p(d_t))}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{d}{N} \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.39}$$

2.3.11. The Chi square goodness of fit test of a neither nor condition relationship

Definition 2.11 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a neither A_t nor B_t condition relationship).

A neither A_t nor B_t condition relationship $p(A_t \downarrow B_t)$ can be tested by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution). The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a neither A_t nor B_t condition relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 may be calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t \downarrow B_t) | A) &\equiv \frac{(d - (c + d))^2}{\underline{A}} + \\
 &\quad \frac{((a + b) - A)^2}{A} \\
 &\equiv \frac{c^2}{\underline{A}} + 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.40}$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t \downarrow B_t) | B) &\equiv \frac{(d - (b + d))^2}{\underline{B}} + \\
 &\quad \frac{((a + c) - B)^2}{B} \\
 &\equiv \frac{b^2}{\underline{B}} + 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.41}$$

Yate's (Yates, 1934) continuity correction has not been used in this context.

2.3.12. The left-tailed p Value of a neither nor B condition relationship

Definition 2.12 (The left-tailed p Value of a neither A_t nor B_t condition relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value (Barukčić, 2019c) of a neither A_t nor B_t condition relationship can be

calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 pValue_{1t}(A_t \downarrow B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t \downarrow B_t))} \\
 &\equiv 1 - e^{-p(A_t \vee B_t)} \\
 &\equiv 1 - e^{-((a+b+c)/N)}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.42}$$

where \vee may denote disjunction or logical inclusive or. In this context, a low p-value indicates again a statistical significance. In general, it is $p(A_t \vee B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \downarrow B_t)$ (see table 7).

Table 7. Neither A_t nor B_t relationship.

		Conditioned B_t		
		YES	NO	
Condition A_t	YES	0	0	0
	NO	0	1	1
		0	1	1

2.3.13. Necessary condition

Definition 2.13 (Necessary condition [Conditio sine qua non]).

Mathematically, the necessary condition (SINE) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (Barukčić, 1989, p. 15-28) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) &\equiv p(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \times p(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)} \\
 &\equiv p(a_t) + p(b_t) + p(d_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(a_t) + p(b_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \leftarrow B_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a + b + d}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{A + d}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \leftarrow B_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a + B}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.43}$$

where $E(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \equiv E(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)$ indicates the expectation value of the necessary condition. In general, it is $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \downarrow B_t)$ (see Table 8).

Remark 2.3. A necessary condition A_t is characterized itself by the property that another event B_t will not occur if A_t is not given, if A_t did not occur (Barukčić, 1989, 1997, 2005, 2016, 2017a,b, 2020a; Barukčić and Ufuoma, 2020; Barukčić, 2020b,c,d). **Example.** A human being cannot live

Table 8. Necessary condition.

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(A_t)$
	FALSE	+0	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

without water. A human being cannot live without gaseous oxygen et cetera. Water itself is a necessary condition of human life. However, gaseous oxygen is a necessary condition of human life too. Thus far, even if water is given and even if water is a necessary condition of human life, without gaseous oxygen there will be no human life. In general, if a conditioned or an outcome B_t depends on the necessary condition A_t and equally on numerous other necessary conditions, an event B_t will not occur if A_t itself is not given independently of the occurrence of other necessary conditions.

2.3.14. The Chi-square goodness of fit test of a necessary condition relationship

Definition 2.14 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a necessary condition relationship).

Under some well known circumstances, hypothesis about the conditio sine qua non relationship $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ can be tested by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or χ^2 -distribution), first described by the German statistician Friedrich Robert Helmert (Helmert, 1876) and later rediscovered by Karl Pearson (Pearson, 1900) in the context of a goodness of fit test. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a conditio sine qua non relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | B) &\equiv \frac{(a - (a + c))^2}{B} + \frac{((b + d) - \underline{B})^2}{\underline{B}} \\ &\equiv \frac{c^2}{B} + 0 \\ &\equiv \frac{c^2}{B} \end{aligned} \quad (2.44)$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | \underline{A}) &\equiv \frac{(d - (c + d))^2}{\underline{A}} + \frac{((a + b) - A)^2}{A} \\ &\equiv \frac{c^2}{\underline{A}} + 0 \\ &\equiv \frac{c^2}{\underline{A}} \end{aligned} \quad (2.45)$$

and can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level of significance α . It has not yet been finally clarified whether the use of Yate's (Yates, 1934) continuity correction is necessary at all.

2.3.15. The left-tailed p Value of the conditio sine qua non relationship

Definition 2.15 (The left-tailed p Value of the conditio sine qua non relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value (Barukčić, 2019c) of the conditio sine qua non relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} pValue_{lt}(A_t \leftarrow B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t \leftarrow B_t))} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-(c/N)} \end{aligned} \quad (2.46)$$

2.3.16. Sufficient condition

Definition 2.16 (Sufficient condition [*Conditio per quam*]).

Mathematically, the sufficient condition (IMP) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (Barukčić, 1989, p. 68-70) as

$$\begin{aligned} p(A_t \rightarrow B_t) &\equiv p(\underline{A}_t \vee B_t) \equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (\underline{A}_t \vee B_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{(\underline{A}_t \vee B_t) \times p(\underline{A}_t \vee B_t)}{(\underline{A}_t \vee B_t)} \\ &\equiv p(a_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) \\ &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(a_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \\ &\equiv \frac{a + c + d}{N} \equiv \frac{E(\underline{A}_t \vee B_t)}{N} \\ &\equiv \frac{B + d}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A_t \rightarrow B_t)}{N} \\ &\equiv \frac{a + A}{N} \\ &\equiv +1 \end{aligned} \quad (2.47)$$

It is $p(A_t \succ B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$ (see Table 9).

Table 9. Sufficient condition.

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	+0	$p(A_t)$
	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

Remark 2.4. A sufficient condition A_t is characterized by the property that another event B_t will occur if A_t is given, if A_t itself occurred (Barukčić, 1989, 1997, 2005, 2016, 2017a,b, 2020a; Barukčić and Ufuoma, 2020; Barukčić, 2020b,c,d). **Example.** The ground, the streets, the trees, human beings and many other objects too will become wet during heavy rain. Especially, **if** it is raining (event A_t), **then** human beings will become wet (event B_t). However, even if this is a common human wisdom, a human being equipped with an appropriate umbrella (denoted by R_t) need not become wet even during heavy rain. An appropriate umbrella (R_t) is similar to an event with the potential to counteract the occurrence of another event (B_t) and can be understood something as an **anti-dot** of another event. In other words, an appropriate umbrella is an antidote of the effect of rain on human body, an appropriate umbrella has the potential to protect humans from the effect of rain on their body. It is a good rule of thumb that the following relationship

$$p(A_t \rightarrow B_t) + p(R_t \wedge B_t) \equiv +1 \quad (2.48)$$

indicates that R_t is an antidote of A_t . However, taking a shower, swimming in a lake et cetera may make human hair wet too. More than anything else, however, these events does not affect the final outcome, the effect of raining on human body.

2.3.17. The Chi square goodness of fit test of a sufficient condition relationship

Definition 2.17 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a sufficient condition relationship).

Under some well known circumstances, testing hypothesis about the conditio per quam relationship $p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$ is possible by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution) too. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a conditio per quam relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \rightarrow B_t | A) &\equiv \frac{(a - (a+b))^2}{A} + \frac{((c+d) - \underline{A})^2}{\underline{A}} \\ &\equiv \frac{b^2}{A} + 0 \\ &\equiv \frac{b^2}{A} \end{aligned} \quad (2.49)$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \rightarrow B_t | B) &\equiv \frac{(d - (b+d))^2}{B} + \frac{((a+c) - B)^2}{B} \\ &\equiv \frac{b^2}{B} + 0 \\ &\equiv \frac{b^2}{B} \end{aligned} \quad (2.50)$$

and can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level of significance α . The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution equals zero when the observed values are equal to the expected/theoretical values of the conditio per quam relationship/distribution $p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$, in which case the null hypothesis is accepted. Yate's (Yates, 1934) continuity correction has not been used in this context.

2.3.18. The left-tailed p Value of the conditio per quam relationship

Definition 2.18 (The left-tailed p Value of the conditio per quam relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value (Barukčić, 2019c) of the conditio per quam relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} pValue_{lt}(A_t \rightarrow B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t \rightarrow B_t))} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-(b/N)} \end{aligned} \quad (2.51)$$

Again, a low p-value indicates a statistical significance.

2.3.19. Necessary and sufficient conditions

Definition 2.19 (Necessary and sufficient conditions [EQV]).

The necessary and sufficient condition (EQV) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (Barukčić, 1989, p. 68-70) as

$$\begin{aligned} p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t) &\equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N ((A_t \vee B_t) \wedge (\underline{A}_t \vee \underline{B}_t))}{N} \\ &\equiv p(a_t) + p(d_t) \\ &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(a_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \\ &\equiv \frac{a + d}{N} \\ &\equiv +1 \end{aligned} \quad (2.52)$$

2.3.20. The Chi square goodness of fit test of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship

Definition 2.20 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship).

Even the necessary and sufficient condition relationship $p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t)$ can be tested by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution) too. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t | A) &\equiv \frac{(a - (a+b))^2}{A} + \\ &\quad \frac{d - ((c+d))^2}{\frac{A}{A}} \\ &\equiv \frac{b^2}{A} + \frac{c^2}{A} \end{aligned} \quad (2.53)$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t | B) &\equiv \frac{(a - (a + c))^2}{B} + \frac{d - ((b + d))^2}{\underline{B}} \\ &\equiv \frac{c^2}{B} + \frac{b^2}{\underline{B}}\end{aligned}\quad (2.54)$$

The calculated $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level of significance α . Under conditions where the observed values are equal to the expected/theoretical values of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship/distribution $p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t)$, the $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution equals zero. It is to be cleared whether Yate's (Yates, 1934) continuity correction should be used at all.

2.3.21. The left-tailed p Value of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship

Definition 2.21 (The left-tailed p Value of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value (Barukčić, 2019c) of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}pValue_{lt}(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t))} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-((b+c)/N)}\end{aligned}\quad (2.55)$$

In this context, a low p-value indicates again a statistical significance. Table 10 may provide an overview of the theoretical distribution of a necessary and sufficient condition.

Table 10. Necessary and sufficient condition.

		Conditioned B_t		
		YES	NO	
Condition A_t	YES	1	0	1
	NO	0	1	1
		1	1	2

2.3.22. Either or conditions

Definition 2.22 (Either A_t or B_t conditions [NEQV]).

Mathematically, an either A_t or B_t condition relationship (NEQV), denoted by $p(A_t \succcurlyeq B_t)$ in terms

of statistics and probability theory, is defined (Barukčić, 1989, p. 68-70) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \succ B_t) &\equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N ((A_t \wedge \underline{B}_t) \vee (\underline{A}_t \wedge B_t))}{N} \\
 &\equiv p(b_t) + p(c_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(b_t) + p(c_t))}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{b + c}{N} \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.56}$$

It is $p(A_t \succ B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t)$ (see Table 11).

Table 11. Either A_t or B_t relationship.

		Conditioned B_t		
		YES	NO	
Condition A_t	YES	0	1	1
	NO	1	0	1
		1	1	2

2.3.23. The Chi-square goodness of fit test of an either or condition relationship

Definition 2.23 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of an either or condition relationship).

An either or condition relationship $p(A_t \succ B_t)$ can be tested by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution) too. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of an either or condition relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t \succ B_t) | A) &\equiv \frac{(b - (a + b))^2}{A} + \\
 &\quad \frac{c - ((c + d))^2}{\underline{A}} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a^2}{A} + \frac{d^2}{\underline{A}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.57}$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t \succ B_t) | B) &\equiv \frac{(c - (a + c))^2}{B} + \\
 &\quad \frac{b - ((b + d))^2}{\underline{B}} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a^2}{B} + \frac{d^2}{\underline{B}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.58}$$

Yate's (Yates, 1934) continuity correction has not been used in this context.

2.3.24. The left-tailed p Value of an either or condition relationship

Definition 2.24 (The left-tailed p Value of an either or condition relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value (Barukčić, 2019c) of an either or condition relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} pValue_{lt}(A_t \succ B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t > B_t))} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-((a+d)/N)} \end{aligned} \quad (2.59)$$

In this context, a low p-value indicates again a statistical significance.

2.3.25. Causal relationship k

Definition 2.25 (Causal relationship k).

Nonetheless, mathematically, the causal (Barukčić, 2011a,b, 2012) relationship (Barukčić, 1989, 1997, 2005, 2016, 2017a) between a cause U_t (German: Ursache) and an effect W_t (German: Wirkung), denoted by $k(U_t, W_t)$, is defined at each single Bernoulli trial t in terms of statistics and probability theory as

$$\begin{aligned} k(U_t, W_t) &\equiv \frac{\sigma(U_t, W_t)}{\sigma(U_t) \times \sigma(W_t)} \\ &\equiv \frac{p(U_t \wedge W_t) - p(U_t) \times p(W_t)}{\sqrt{(p(U_t) \times (1 - p(U_t))) \times (p(W_t) \times (1 - p(W_t)))}} \end{aligned} \quad (2.60)$$

where $\sigma(U_t, W_t)$ denotes the co-variance between a cause U_t and an effect W_t at every single Bernoulli trial t , $\sigma(U_t)$ denotes the standard deviation of a cause U_t at the same single Bernoulli trial t , $\sigma(W_t)$ denotes the standard deviation of an effect W_t at same single Bernoulli trial t . Table 12 illustrates the theoretically possible relationships between a cause and an effect.

Table 12. Sample space and the causal relationship k

		Effect B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Cause A_t	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(U_t)$
	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{U}_t)$
		$p(W_t)$	$p(\underline{W}_t)$	+1

2.3.26. Study design and bias

Systematic observation and experimentation, inductive and deductive reasoning are essential for any formation and testing of hypotheses and theories about the natural world. In one way or another, logically and mathematically sound scientific methods and concepts are crucial constituents of any

scientific progress. When all goes well, different scientists at different times and places using the same scientific methodology should be able to generate the same scientific knowledge. However, more than half (52%) of scientists surveyed believe that studies do not successfully reproduce sufficiently similar or the same results as the original studies (Baker, 2016). In a very large study on publication bias in meta-analyses, Kicinski et al. (Kicinski et al., 2015) found evidence of publication bias even in systematic reviews. Therefore, a careful re-evaluation of the study/experimental design, the statistical methods and other scientific means which underpin scientific inquiry and research goals appears to be necessary once and again. While it is important to recognise the shortcoming of today's science, one issue which has shaped debates over studies published is the question: **has a study really measured what it set out to?** Even if studies carried out can vary greatly in detail, the data from the studies itself provide information about the credibility of the data.

Index of unfairness (IOU)

Definition 2.26 (Index of unfairness).

The index of unfairness (Barukčić, 2019a) (IOU) is defined as

$$p(\text{IOU}(A, B)) \equiv \text{Absolute} \left(\left(\frac{A+B}{N} \right) - 1 \right) \quad (2.61)$$

A very good study design should assure as much as possible a $p(\text{IOU}) = 0$. In point of fact, against the background of lacking enough experience with the use of $p(\text{IOU})$, a $p(\text{IOU})$ up to 0.25 could be of use too. An index of unfairness is of use to prove whether sample data are biased and whether sample data can be used for Chi-square based analysis of necessary conditions, of sufficient conditions and of causal relationships.

Index of independence (IOI)

Definition 2.27 (Index of independence).

The index of independence (Barukčić, 2019b) (IOI) is defined as

$$p(\text{IOI}(A, \underline{B})) \equiv \text{Absolute} \left(\left(\frac{A+\underline{B}}{N} \right) - 1 \right) \quad (2.62)$$

A very good study design which aims to prove **an exclusion relationship or a causal relationship** should assure as much as possible a $p(\text{IOI}) = 0$. However, once again, against the background of lacking enough experience with the use of $p(\text{IOI})$, sample data with a $p(\text{IOI})$ up to 0.25 are of use too. Today, most double-blind placebo-controlled studies are based on the demand that **$p(\text{IOU}) = p(\text{IOI})$** while the value of $p(\text{IOU})$ of has been widely neglected. Such an approach leads to unnecessary big sample sizes, the increase of cost, the waste of time and, most importantly of all, to epistemological systematically biased sample data and conclusions drawn. A change is necessary.

Index of relationship (IOR)

Definition 2.28 (Index of relationship (IOR)).

Due to several reasons, it is not always easy to identify the unique characteristics between two events like A_t and B_t . And more than that, it is difficult to decide what to do, and much more difficult to know in which direction one should think and which decision is right. Sometimes it is helpful to know at least something about the direction of the relationship between two events like A_t and B_t . Under conditions where $p(a_t) = p(A_t \wedge B_t)$, the index of relationship (Barukčić, 2021a), abbreviated as IOR, is defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
 IOR(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \left(\frac{p(A_t \wedge B_t)}{p(B_t) \times p(A_t)} \right) - 1 \\
 &\equiv \left(\frac{p(a_t)}{p(B_t) \times p(A_t)} \right) - 1 \\
 &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{N \times N \times p(a_t)}{N \times p(B_t) \times N \times p(A_t)} \right) - 1 \right) \\
 &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{N \times a}{A \times B} \right) - 1 \right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.63}$$

where $p(A_t)$ denotes the probability of an event A_t at the Bernoulli trial t and $p(B_t)$ denotes the probability of another event B_t at the same Bernoulli trial t while $p(a_t)$ denotes the joint probability of $p(A_t \text{ AND } B_t)$ at the same Bernoulli trial t and a , A and B may denote the expectation values.

2.3.27. relative risk (RR)

Relative risk (RR_{nc})

Definition 2.29 (Relative risk (RR_{nc})).

The degree of association between the two binomial variables can be assessed by a number of very different coefficients, the relative (Cornfield, 1951; Sadowsky et al., 1953) risk is one (Barukčić, 2021b) of them. In general, relative risk RR_{nc} , which provides some evidence of a necessary condition, is defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
 RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} &= \frac{\frac{p(a_t)}{p(A_t)}}{\frac{p(c_t)}{p(NotA_t)}} = \frac{p(a_t) \times p(NotA_t)}{p(c_t) \times p(A_t)} = \frac{N \times p(a_t) \times N \times p(NotA_t)}{N \times p(c_t) \times N \times p(A_t)} = \frac{a_t \times (NotA_t)}{c_t \times A_t} = \frac{EER(A_t, B_t)}{CER(A_t, B_t)}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.64}$$

That what scientist generally understand by relative risk is the ratio of a probability of an event occurring with an exposure versus the probability of an event occurring without an exposure. In other words,

relative risk = (probability(event in exposed group)) / (probability(the same event in not exposed group)).

A $RR(A_t, B_t) = +1$ means that exposure does not affect the outcome or both are independent of each other while $RR(A_t, B_t)$ less than $+1$ means that the risk of the outcome is decreased by the exposure. In this context, an $RR(A_t, B_t)$ greater than $+1$ denotes that the risk of the outcome is increased by the exposure. Widely known problems with odds ratio and relative risk are already documented in literature.

Relative risk (RR (sc))

Definition 2.30 (Relative risk (RR (sc))).

The relative risk (sc), which provides some evidence of a sufficient condition, is calculated from the point of view of an outcome and is defined as

$$RR(A_t, B_t)_{sc} = \frac{\frac{p(a_t)}{p(B_t)}}{\frac{p(b_t)}{p(NotB_t)}} = \frac{p(a_t) \times p(NotB_t)}{p(b_t) \times p(B_t)} = \frac{N \times p(a_t) \times N \times p(NotB_t)}{N \times p(b_t) \times N \times p(B_t)} = \frac{a_t \times (NotB_t)}{b_t \times B_t} = \frac{OPR(A_t, B_t)}{CPR(A_t, B_t)} \quad (2.65)$$

Relative risk reduction (RRR)

Definition 2.31 (Relative risk reduction (RRR)).

$$\begin{aligned} RRR(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \frac{CER(A_t, B_t) - EER(A_t, B_t)}{CER(A_t, B_t)} \\ &= 1 - RR(A_t, B_t) \end{aligned} \quad (2.66)$$

Vaccine efficacy (VE)

Definition 2.32 (Vaccine efficacy (VE)).

Vaccine efficacy is defined as the percentage reduction of a disease in a vaccinated group of people as compared to an unvaccinated group of people.

$$\begin{aligned} VE(A_t, B_t) &\equiv 100 \times (1 - RR(A_t, B_t)) \\ &\equiv 100 \times \left(\frac{CER(A_t, B_t) - EER(A_t, B_t)}{CER(A_t, B_t)} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (2.67)$$

Historically, vaccine efficacy has been designed to evaluate the efficacy of a certain vaccine by Greenwood and Yule in 1915 for the cholera and typhoid vaccines (Greenwood and Yule, 1915) and best measured using double-blind, randomized, clinical controlled trials. However, the calculated vaccine efficacy is depending too much on the study design, can lead to erroneous conclusions and is only of very limited value.

Experimental event rate (EER)

Definition 2.33 (Experimental event rate (EER)).

$$EER(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{p(a_t)}{p(A_t)} = \frac{a_t}{a_t + b_t} \quad (2.68)$$

Definition 2.34 (Control event rate (CER)).

$$CER(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{p(c_t)}{p(\underline{A}_t)} = \frac{c_t}{c_t + d_t} \quad (2.69)$$

Absolute risk reduction (ARR)

Definition 2.35 (Absolute risk reduction (ARR)).

$$\begin{aligned} ARR(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \frac{p(c_t)}{p(\underline{A}_t)} - \frac{p(a_t)}{p(A_t)} \\ &= \frac{c_t}{c_t + d_t} - \frac{a_t}{a_t + b_t} \\ &= CER(A_t, B_t) - EER(A_t, B_t) \end{aligned} \quad (2.70)$$

Absolute risk increase (ARI)

Definition 2.36 (Absolute risk increase (ARI)).

$$\begin{aligned} ARI(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \frac{p(a_t)}{p(A_t)} - \frac{p(c_t)}{p(\underline{A}_t)} \\ &= EER(A_t, B_t) - CER(A_t, B_t) \end{aligned} \quad (2.71)$$

Number needed to treat (NNT)

Definition 2.37 (Number needed to treat (NNT)).

$$NNT(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{1}{CER(A_t, B_t) - EER(A_t, B_t)} \quad (2.72)$$

An ideal number needed to treat (Laupacis et al., 1988; Cook and Sackett, 1995), mathematically the reciprocal of the absolute risk reduction, is $NNT = 1$. Under these circumstances, everyone improves with a treatment, while no one improves with control. A higher number needed to treat indicates more or less a treatment which is less effective.

Number needed to harm (NNH)

Definition 2.38 (Number needed to harm (NNH)).

$$NNH(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{1}{EER(A_t, B_t) - CER(A_t, B_t)} \quad (2.73)$$

The number needed to harm (Massel and Cruickshank, 2002), mathematically the inverse of the absolute risk increase, indicates at the end how many patients need to be exposed to a certain factor, in order to observe a harm in one patient that would not otherwise have been harmed.

Outcome prevalence rate (OPR)

Definition 2.39 (Outcome prevalence rate (OPR)).

$$OPR(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{p(a_t)}{p(B_t)} = \frac{a_t}{a_t + c_t} \quad (2.74)$$

Control prevalence rate (CPR)

Definition 2.40 (Control prevalence rate (CPR)).

$$CPR(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{p(b_t)}{p(\underline{B}_t)} = \frac{b_t}{b_t + d_t} \quad (2.75)$$

Bias and confounding is present to some degree in all research. In order to assess the relationship of exposure with a disease or an outcome, a fictive control group (i.e. of newborn or of young children et cetera) can be of use too. Under certain circumstances, even a $CPR = 0$ is imaginable.

Absolute prevalence reduction (APR)

Definition 2.41 (Absolute prevalence reduction (APR)).

$$APR(A_t, B_t) \equiv CPR(A_t, B_t) - OPR(A_t, B_t) \quad (2.76)$$

Absolute prevalence increase (API)

Definition 2.42 (Absolute prevalence increase (API)).

$$API(A_t, B_t) \equiv OPR(A_t, B_t) - CPR(A_t, B_t) \quad (2.77)$$

Relative prevalence reduction (RPR)

Definition 2.43 (Relative prevalence reduction (RPR)).

$$\begin{aligned} RPR(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \frac{CPR(A_t, B_t) - OPR(A_t, B_t)}{CPR(A_t, B_t)} \\ &= 1 - RR(A_t, B_t)_{sc} \end{aligned} \quad (2.78)$$

The index NNS

Definition 2.44 (The index NNS).

$$NNS(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{1}{CPR(A_t, B_t) - OPR(A_t, B_t)} \quad (2.79)$$

Mathematically, the index NNS is the reciprocal of the absolute prevalence reduction.

The index NNI

Definition 2.45 (The index NNI).

$$NNI(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{1}{OPR(A_t, B_t) - CPR(A_t, B_t)} \quad (2.80)$$

Mathematically, the index NNI is the reciprocal of the absolute prevalence increase.

2.3.28. Odds ratio (OR)

Definition 2.46 (Odds ratio (OR)).

Odds ratios as an appropriate measure for estimating the relative risk have become widely used in medical reports of case-control studies. The odds ratio (Fisher, 1935, p. 50) is defined (Cox, 1958) as the ratio of the odds of an event occurring in one group with respect to the odds of its occurring in another group. Odds (Yule and Pearson, 1900, p. 273) ratio (OR) is a measure of association which quantifies the relationship between two binomial distributed random variables (exposure vs. outcome) and is related to Yule's (Yule and Pearson, 1900, p. 272) Q (Yule, 1912, p. 585/586). Two events A_t and B_t are regarded as independent if $(A_t, B_t) = 1$. Let

a_t = number of persons exposed to A_t and with disease B_t

b_t = number of persons exposed to A_t but without disease B_t

c_t = number of persons unexposed A_t but with disease B_t

d_t = number of persons unexposed A_t : and without disease B_t

$a_t + c_t$ = total number of persons with disease B_t (case-patients)

$b_t + d_t$ = total number of persons without disease B_t (controls).

Hereafter, consider the table 13. The odds' ratio (OR) is defined as

Table 13. The two by two table of random variables

		Conditioned/Outcome B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition/Exposure A_t	TRUE	a_t	b_t	A_t
	FALSE	c_t	d_t	\underline{A}_t
		B_t	\underline{B}_t	N_t

$$\begin{aligned}
 OR(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \left(\frac{a_t}{b_t}\right) / \left(\frac{c_t}{d_t}\right) \\
 &\equiv \left(\frac{a_t \times d_t}{b_t \times c_t}\right)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{2.81}$$

Remark 2.5. Odds ratios can support logical fallacies and cause difficulties in drawing logically consistent conclusions. The chorus of voices is growing, which demand the immediate ending (Sackett *et al.*, 1996; Knol, 2012) of any use of Odds ratio.

Under conditions where ($b = 0$), the measure of association odds ratio will collapse, because we need to divide by zero, as can be seen at eq. 2.81. However, according to today's rules of mathematics, a division by zero is neither allowed nor generally accepted as possible. It does no harm to remind ourselves that in the case $b = 0$ the event A_t is a sufficient condition of B_t . In other words, odds ratio is not able to recognize elementary relationships of objective reality. In fact, it would be a failure not to recognize how dangerous and less valuable odds ratio is.

Under conditions where ($c = 0$) odds ratio collapses too, because we need again to divide by zero, as can be seen at eq. 2.81. However, and again, today's rules of mathematics don't allow us a division by zero. In point of fact, in the case $c = 0$ it is more than necessary to point out that A_t is a necessary condition of B_t . In other words, odds ratio or the cross-product ratio is not able to recognize elementary relationships of nature like necessary conditions. We can and need to overcome all the epistemological obstacles as backed by odds ratio entirety. Sooner rather than later, we should give up this measure of relationship completely.

2.4. Statistical methods

The probability of the necessary (Barukčić, 2021c) condition p(SINE) has been calculated and tested for statistical significance. The probability of the sufficient (Barukčić, 2021c) condition p(IMP) has been calculated, the statistical significance of this relationship has been proofed. The chi-square goodness of fit test with one degree of freedom has been used to test whether the sample data published fit a certain theoretical distribution in the population. The causal relationship k (Barukčić, 2021c) has been calculated to evaluate a possible causal relationship between the events/factors analysed. The hyper-geometric (Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Pearson, 1899; Fisher, 1922; Gonin, 1936) distribution (HGD) has been used to test the one-sided significance of the causal relationship k . The study (design) bias has been controlled by IOI, the index of independence (Barukčić, 2019b) and IOU, the index of unfairness (Barukčić, 2019a). All the data were analysed using MS Excel (Microsoft Corporation, USA). The p values less than 0.05 were considered to indicate a statistically significant difference.

2.5. Axioms

2.5.1. Axiom I. Lex identitatis

In this context, we define axiom I as the expression

$$+ 1 = +1 \quad (2.82)$$

2.5.2. Axiom II. Lex contradictionis

In this context, axiom II or **lex contradictionis**, the negative of lex identitatis, or

$$+ 0 = +1 \quad (2.83)$$

and equally the most simple form of a contradiction formulated.

2.5.3. Axiom III. Lex negationis

$$\neg(0) \times 0 = 1 \quad (2.84)$$

where \neg denotes (logical (Boole, 1854) or natural) negation (Royce, 1917; Heinemann, 1943; Ayer, 1952; Hedwig, 1980; Kunen, 1987; Wedin, 1990; Koch, 1999; Horn, 1989; Speranza and Horn, 2010; Förster and Melamed, 2012; Newstadt, 2015). In this context, there is some evidence that $\neg(1) \times 1 = 0$. In other words, it is $(\neg(1) \times 1) \times (\neg(0) \times 0) = 1$

3. Results

3.1. Ritonavir excludes Covid-19 death

Theorem 3.1 (Ritonavir excludes Covid-19 death). **CLAIM.**

Null-Hypothesis:

*Ritonavir **does exclude** (Covid-19) death.*

Alternative Hypothesis:

*Ritonavir **does not exclude** (Covid-19) death.*

Proof by the data of Pfizer Inc. The data ¹⁹ and the statistical analysis on the relationship between ritonavir and (Covid-19) death are presented by table 2. The causal relationship is negative and highly significant ($k=-0.0905744038$; p Value left tailed (HGD)=0.0009805; IOR = -1). The index of independence is $p(\text{IOI}) = 0.489745693$. In other words, the study design is very unfair. The exclusion relationship is $p(\text{EXCL})= 1$ and highly significant (p Value (EXCL)=0). Summarized, the null-hypothesis cannot be rejected. Ritonavir **does exclude** (Covid-19) death ($p(\text{EXCL})= 1$, p Value (EXCL)=0).

□

4. Discussion

Data quality (DQ) is the degree to which a given dataset meets with the requirements of objective reality. Poor quality data are dangerous and can negatively affect the reproducibility and validity of research results and limit the validity of the conclusion drawn. However, the study design as such can be a source of errors too, making it even impossible to extract any reliable and useful information from data. Therefore, the quality of data we are working with should be constantly assessed and even reassessed to ensure appropriate levels of quality of data. Today, it is difficult to say anything about the quality of data as announced by Pfizer, Inc²⁰. Under the circumstance that the data as published by Pfizer, Inc. are at least of average value, the conclusion is inescapable.

5. Conclusion

The drug ritonavir **does exclude** (Covid-19) death.

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6. Patient consent for publication

Not required.

¹⁹Pfizer™ Inc., Friday, November 05, 2021 - 06:45am

²⁰Pfizer™ Inc., Friday, November 05, 2021 - 06:45am

Conflict of interest statement

No conflict of interest to declare.

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I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality**.

^a<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6988-2780>

^bhttps://cel.webofknowledge.com/InboundService.do?app=wos&product=CEL&Func=Frame&SrcApp=Publons&SrcAuth=Publons_CEL&locale=en-US&SID=F4r5Tsr30crmFbYrqiF&customersID=Publons_CEL&smartRedirect=yes&mode=FullRecord&IsProductCode=Yes&Init=Yes&action=retrieve&UT=WOS%3A000298855300006

^c<https://publons.com/researcher/3501739/ilija-barukcic/>

^d<https://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.uri?authorId=37099674500>

^e<https://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.uri?authorId=54974181600>

^f<https://www.mendeley.com/search/?authorFullName=Ilija%20Baruk%C4%8Di%C4%87&page=1&query=Barukcic&sortBy=relevance>

^g<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Ilija-Barukcic-2>

^h<https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=keywords:%22Baruk%C4%8Di%C4%87%22&sort=mostviewed>

ⁱ<https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=keywords:%22Baruk%C4%8Di%C4%87,%20Conference%22>

^j<https://twitter.com/ilijabarukcic?lang=de>

^khttps://twitter.com/Causation_Journ

^lhttps://vixra.org/author/ilija_barukcic

^m<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCwf3w1IngcukI00jpw8HTwg>

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